

POLY (VINYLIDENE FLUORIDE)/MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBE COMPOSITES: POLYMORPHS TRANSFORMATION INDUCED DUCTILITY

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ABSTRACT

Poly (vinylidene fluoride)/multi-walled carbon nanotube (PVDF/MWCNTs) composites with different filler loadings were fabricated via a combined method of solution mixing and melt blending. Excellent CNT dispersion was seen by electron microscopy. With very low CNT content, prepared composites display significantly enhanced ductility as compared with neat PVDF which results in largely increased fracture toughness with the context of no loss in modulus. With as low as 0.2 wt. % CNT loading, the elongation at break has been almost quadrupled. Investigations show that the elevated ductility (toughness) originates from the polymorphs transformation of PVDF matrix. A minor γ phase PVDF was obtained in composite samples and this phase gradually disappeared with the development of stretching. It is believed that this γ phase continue to feed and transformed into β crystalline during the stretching. The disassembly of γ phase and re-assembly into β phase create a plasticized section around CNT. This plasticizing zone-like section leads to striking increase of ductility of the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer-matrix composites (PMCs), combining both the advantages of polymer and specific properties of fillers, have found numerous applications¹⁻⁴. Although polymer composites have been studied for long, the emergence of new generation of nano scale fillers, such as nanoclay, CNTs and carbon nanofibers, reanimated this topic in recent years. Due to their unique size dependent features, polymer composites incorporating these kinds of fillers often display exceptional mechanical⁵⁻⁹, thermal¹⁰⁻¹², rheological¹³, electrical^{14, 15}, optical¹⁶⁻¹⁸ and self healing^{19, 20} properties. Despite the many outstanding properties that been realized in polymer matrix composites, the mechanical performance remains most important.

CNTs improve the property of crystalline thermoplastics largely related to CNT-induced polymer crystallization. Diversified ways are continue to be discovered in which CNTs affect the crystalline of

polymers due to their particular configuration, dimension and surface property. CNTs can induce nanohybrid shish-kebab (NHSKs), a crystalline structure that consisting of a central fibril and multiple disc-like, folded-chain lamellae orthogonal to the shish in many polymers, such as polyethylene²¹, nylon 6,6²², poly-L-lysine and PVDF²³. It is believed that in NHSKs the kebab crystals not only the serving as spacers prevent CNTs from aggregation but working as nano-anchors beneficial to load transfer between polymer matrix and fillers²⁴. Transcrystallinity (TC) is another form of crystalline structure that can be generated by the interaction between CNT and crystalline polymers²⁵. In TC, crystalline grows perpendicularly to the filler surfaces and form columnar crystalline layer around tabular fillers. As early as 1952, research has been carrying out on TC and quite a few polymers such as polypropylene, polyethylene, poly (ether ether ketone), poly (phenylene sulfide) and polyamide have been reported on TC structure using various fillers²⁶. Albeit the debates on detailed effects of TC on mechanical property of these polymers due to lack of measurements, it is accepted that the TC structure exerts heavy influences on interfaces in polymer composites owing to its anisotropy and consequently affect significantly the mechanical performance of final products.

In this study, semi-crystalline thermoplastic PVDF composites filled with MWCNTs were prepared and investigated regarding polymorphs and mechanical property. The morphology of prepared samples was studied with field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM). SEM samples were prepared by firstly immersing samples inside liquid nitrogen to prepare cyro-fractured surface and then coated with platinum for 45 s before investigated by JEOL JSM-7600F.

2 RESULTS AND DISSCUSSION

Figure 1: Fabrication illustration of melt extrusion and SEM images of yielding products.

To compare the effect of different methods on the mechanical properties of PVDF composites, three approaches have been employed in this study. First, melt extrusion was used to prepare PVDF/CNTs composites. The illustration of the fabrication process is shown in Figure 1. Initially, the CNTs powder and PVDF powder were pre-mixed before extrusion. After 10 mins extrusion at 180 °C, the products were hot pressed into thin films with 0.2 mm thickness. Figure 1 shows the cryo-fracture images. It can be seen CNTs form aggregates with diameter in several micrometers.

Figure 2: Tensile test of pure PVDF prepared from melt extrusion.

Figure 3: Tensile test of PVDF composites with 0.2 wt. % CNTs prepared from melt extrusion.

Figure 2 and 3 shows the tensile test results of pure PVDF and PVDF composite with 0.2 wt. % CNTs. It can be seen there is no much change on the tensile strength and modulus after the introduction of CNTs. However, the elongation at break largely decreased in the composite sample, which is believed to be the result of the CNTs aggregations. It is known that the CNTs aggregates can largely damage the mechanical performance of final products due to stress concentration.

Figure 4: Fabrication illustration of solution blending and SEM images of yielding products.

Solution blending was also used to prepare PVDF/CNTs composites. The illustration of the fabrication process is shown in Figure 4. Initially, CNTs was dispersed in acetone by ultrasound sonication. At the same time, PVDF was dissolved in acetone. Then, the two solutions were mixed via ultrasound sonication. PVDF/CNTs can be obtained by casting the mixed solution in petri-dish and evacuating the solvents. After that, the obtained products were hot pressed into thin films with 0.2 mm thickness. Figure 4 shows the cryo-fracture images. It can be seen most of the tubes are individually dispersed. However, the distribution of CNTs is not uniform. Some regions have much more CNTs than others.

Figure 5: Tensile test of pure PVDF prepared from solution blending.

Figure 6: Tensile test of PVDF composites with 0.2 wt. % CNTs prepared from solution blending.

Figure 5 and 6 shows the tensile test results of pure PVDF and PVDF composite with 0.2 wt. % CNTs prepared from solution blending. It can be seen there is no much change on the tensile strength and modulus after the introduction of CNTs. The elongation at break of pure PVDF largely increased compared with that of the products made from melt extrusion. This might be because of the trapped solvent molecules in the polymer matrix. In addition, the tensile strength of the samples with or without CNTs decreased using the solution blending approach, further support the postulation that solvent molecular can be trapped in the polymer and affects the mechanical properties.

Figure 7: Fabrication illustration of combined method and SEM images of yielding products.

At last, the combined method that containing both solution blending and melt extrusion was used to prepare PVDF/CNTs composites. The illustration of the fabrication process is shown in Figure 7. Briefly, the products made from solution blending were further melt extruded before the hot press. Figure 7 shows the cryo-fracture images. It can be seen most of the tubes are individually dispersed and evenly distributed in the polymer matrix.

Figure 8: Tensile test of pure PVDF prepared from combined method.

Figure 9: Tensile test of PVDF composites with 0.2 wt. % CNTs prepared from combined method.

Figure 8 and 9 shows the tensile test results of pure PVDF and PVDF composite with 0.2 wt. % CNTs prepared from the combining method. It can be seen there is no much change on the tensile

strength and modulus after the introduction of CNTs. However, the elongation at break was largely enhanced.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Three different approaches have been employed to fabricate PVDF/CNTs composites. It was found that the melt extrusion results in CNTs aggregations while solution blending can not enable even distribution of the nanofillers in polymer matrix. The combining method can improve both the dispersion and distribution of CNTs in PVDF. Tensile tests shows that CNTs with good dispersion and distribution may largely enhance the ductility while not damage the tensile strength and modulus.

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